

TEACHER'S OCCUPATIONAL STRESS- HINDI ADAPTATION

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out on 600 School/college Teachers to determine the psychometric characteristics i.e. objectivity, reliability, validity and practicability of a bilingual (English and Hindi) Teacher's Occupational Stress scale. The responses are on a Likert type pattern. Cronbach's Alpha of the scale was 0.91, which is excellent. Content validity of the scale was verified by a number of experts, academicians and professionals. Using a more structured method, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was carried out and three (3) factors emerged in the analysis. In summing up all three factors explained 50.55% of the total variance which confirms the very high factorial/construct validity. Further, inter-factorial correlations among sub dimensions of Teacher's Occupational Stress scale found highly significant. It can be concluded that the present piece of research work confirms high objectivity, reliability, validity and practicability of Teacher's Occupational Stress scale. Conclusion drawn, uses for training, assessment, and intervention and research purposes proposed.

Keywords: *Teacher's Occupational Stress, Reliability, Validity.*

Introduction

The term "stress" was first introduced by Hans Selye, who characterized it as a process in which environmental forces threaten an individual's well-being. The researcher (Selye, 1976) further defined stress as a physiological non-specific reaction to external or internal demands.

Stress is a state of mental or emotional strain or suspense, and; a number of normal reactions of the body (mental, emotional, and physiological) designed for self-preservation (Princeton University, 2001). Despite its diffuse perception, most of the well-known definitions emphasize stress as any factor that threatens the health of an individual or has an adverse effect on the functioning of the body (Oxford Medical Publications, 1985). Stress is a perception phenomenon which exists from a comparison between the command given and ability of a person to execute the task successfully. Unbalanced situation in this mechanism leads to stress experience and ultimately into stress reaction (Cox & Brockley, 1984).

Stress, in general, and occupational stress, in particular, is a fact of modern day life that seems to have been increasing. Stress is an unavoidable characteristic of life and work. Work-related stress is defined as, "a pattern of emotional, cognitive, behavioral and physiological reactions to adverse and noxious aspects of work content, work organization and work environment" (European Commission, 2002). Stress involving work is termed as Occupational Stress. It occurs when there is discrepancy between the demands of the workplace and that of individual's (Tsutsumi et al., 2009). Beehr and Newman (1978) defined occupational stress as a stimulus wherein the job related factors interact with the workers to change (i.e., or enhance) his/ her psychological and/ or physiological condition so that the person (i.e., mind/ body) is forced to deviate from normal functioning. Occupational stress

describes physical, mental and emotional wear and tear brought about by incongruence between the requirement of the job and the capabilities, resources and needs of the employee to cope with job demands (Akinboye, Akinboye, & Adeyemo, 2002).

Occupational Stress, also known as job stress, has been defined as the experience of negative emotional states such as frustration, worry, anxiety and depression attributed to work related factors (Kyriacou, 2001). It is a mental and physical condition which affects an individual's productivity, effectiveness, personal health and quality of work (Comish & Swindle, 1994). Geese and Moss (2001) define the occupational stress as a mutual action between the working conditions and individual features of a worker. It is defined as a result of imbalance between job demands and workers' capabilities. Also, harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker, can be termed as occupational stress (NIOSH, 2008). Occupational stress is an individual experience, depending on the traits of individuals, in that not all people react to events the same way (Manthei & Gilmore, 1996; McKenna, 1987). Bendell et al. (1986) state that occupational stress is a potential tormenting reaction which the worker shows towards a stress organic factor.

Occupational role stress is considered as an unpleasant emotion, which manifests itself through tension, frustration, anxiety, anger and depression. All these emotions are the result of different aspects of working environment and personal lives of the universities teachers (Khurshid, 2008).

Development of the Scale

At the onset experts in the field of Psychology, Education and Sociology were contacted and the objective of developing the scale explained to them. Including their input, three dimensions of Teacher's Occupational Scale were decided, and were as follows:

1. Work Characteristics
2. Situational Characteristics
3. Personal Characteristics

Teacher stress is a negative response or an unpleasant emotion such as anger, irritation, and resentment. Usually accompanied by physiological and biochemical changes resulting from aspects of the teacher's work, and mediated by the perception that the demands made upon the teacher comprise a threat to his/her well-being or self-esteem.

Operational Definitions

Teacher's occupational stress: Teacher's occupational stress is stress related to their job. Occupational stress often stems from unexpected/ambiguous responsibilities and pressures that do not align with a teacher's knowledge, skills, or expectations, inhibiting teacher's ability to cope.

Work Characteristics: Aspects specific to a work (school environment, colleague), knowledge and skills, mental and physical demands, and working duration that can be recognized, defined, and assessed as work characteristics.

Situational Characteristics: A person or thing in regards to surroundings or circumstances and how a person reacts in different environments and situation.

Personal Characteristics: These characteristics are what make up one's personality. They help a person get along in new circumstances.

First Draft of the Scale & Item Analysis

In the first phase, a pool of 25 items keeping in consideration the operational definition of proposed construct was prepared with Likert type, 5-point response, viz., *Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree*. This scale was administered on a representative sample of 300 school/college Teachers of Uttar Pradesh, India whose age was varying from 24 to 62 years.

After scoring the sheets, the data was arranged in the order of highest score to lowest score. From this order, two groups, one of 27% from highest scoring and other of 27% from the lowest scoring were selected. In these two groups inter-correlation matrix was examined in order to overcome existence of multicollinearity and singularity in the scale. In addition to inter-correlation matrix, 'Determinant' of the R-matrix was estimated and it was greater than 0.00001 (i.e. 0.001), which is pre-requisite. Sampling adequacy through Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test was also examined and found to be greater than 0.50 (i.e. 0.932). On this basis six (6) items having multicollinearity and singularity were rejected and the final manuscript of the scale had 19 items distributed across three dimensions emerged through Exploratory Factor analysis. The distribution of items and dimensions is given in Table 1.

Table 1.
Teacher's Occupational Stress dimensions and No. of items

No.	Dimensions	Items	Total	No. of items
1	Work Characteristics (X1)	1, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 15,	10	
2	Situational Characteristics (X2)	4, 6, 16, 12, 14, 20	6	
3	Personal Characteristics (X3)	17, 18, 19	3	
Total Items			19	

Scoring System

All items are positively worded and scored as per criterion shown in table 2.

Table 2
Scoring System

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

The responses of the corresponding items were added to generate *Teacher's Occupational Stress* dimension scores and summing-up all 19 items to make overall *Teacher's Occupational Stress* score. Thus, the minimum possible score will be 19 and the maximum 95 for the scale. Higher the score indicates high level of *Teacher's Occupational Stress* and lower the score indicates low level of *Teacher's Occupational Stress*.

Standardization of the Scale

The final manuscript of *Teacher's Occupational Stress* administered on 600 teachers selected from 70 Schools/colleges situated in Different Districts of Uttar Pradesh of India. Their age varied from 24 to 62 years with mean age 32.42 years. Working experience varied from 3 to 41 years with mean 9.52 years. In qualification they were TGT (Trained Graduate Teacher), PGT (Post Graduate Teacher) and others (BTC, NT, AST) of government and private schools/colleges.

Target population of this study was school/college teachers, in which some Trained Graduate Teacher (TGT), Post Graduate Teacher (PGT), Basic Training Certificate (BTC), Nursery Teachers (NT) and Assistant Teachers of Government as well as Private Schools/college were taken. Some of them were teaching at the level of Elementary, some of them at Secondary level and remaining at the Senior Secondary level. Researcher includes Science, Arts and Commerce stream teachers. Most of the teachers were married.

Instructions for Administration

Instructions for administration have been printed on the cover of the scale. The scale can be administered on an individual or on a group (preferably not more than 30 at a time) on teacher's population.

Reliability

The considerations of reliability and validity typically are viewed as essential elements for determining the quality of any standardized test. However, professional and practitioner associations frequently have placed these concerns within broader contexts when developing standards and making overall judgments about the quality of any standardized test as a whole within a given context. For establishing the internal consistency reliability: Cronbach's alpha is estimated and is shown in Table 3 & 4.

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics of items, scale and Alpha

Item No.	Descriptive Statistics for Items				Descriptive Statistics for Scale			
	Range	Mean	SD	Var	Scale Mean if item deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	*Item total correlation	*Alpha if item deleted
OS1	4	1.64	1.017	1.033	33.44	136.676	.556	.901
OS2	4	2.02	1.134	1.287	33.05	134.093	.591	.900
OS3	4	1.77	.940	.884	33.30	139.662	.468	.904
OS4	4	2.06	1.208	1.460	33.01	132.600	.606	.900
OS5	4	1.71	.884	.782	33.36	140.003	.485	.903
OS6	4	1.95	1.076	1.158	33.13	134.379	.617	.900
OS7	4	1.72	.951	.905	33.35	137.843	.545	.902
OS8	4	2.06	1.252	1.567	33.01	133.177	.560	.902
OS9	4	1.74	1.042	1.086	33.33	136.715	.539	.902
OS10	4	1.71	1.091	1.189	33.37	136.800	.507	.903
OS11	4	1.59	.836	.699	33.48	139.758	.530	.902
OS12	4	1.67	.967	.935	33.40	134.134	.708	.898
OS13	4	1.80	.946	.894	33.28	136.581	.609	.900
OS14	4	1.82	1.091	1.191	33.26	132.352	.692	.898
OS15	4	1.59	.888	.789	33.49	138.334	.566	.901
OS16	4	2.49	1.380	1.903	32.59	134.099	.468	.905
OS17	4	2.08	1.275	1.627	33.00	134.851	.488	.904
OS18	4	1.71	.937	.877	33.36	136.577	.616	.900
OS19	4	1.92	1.025	1.051	33.16	138.790	.461	.904

* $r=.07$ ($p<.05$), $.10$ ($p<.01$), $.13$ ($p<.001$)- Two Tailed

Table 4

Descriptive statistics of scale and Reliability (Cronbach's Alpha)

Statistics for Scale	Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	Alpha Coefficient	No. of Items
	35.08	150.945	12.286	0.906	19

One of the most commonly used reliability coefficient i.e. Cronbach's Alpha was calculated and found 0.906, significant at 0.001 levels. The internal consistency of the scale is excellent and this gives a support that the scale is highly reliable. Inter-correlations among dimensions of the scale are given in Table 5.

Table 5

Inter-factorial validity, Cronbach's Alpha and Effect-Size Dimension wise

Dimensions	Factors			Reliability (α)	Effect-size
	X1	X2	X3		
Work Characteristics (X1)	1			0.825	0.680
Social Characteristics (X2)	.893**	1		0.787	0.619
Personal Characteristics (X3)	.608**	.703**	1	0.790	0.624

* $r=.07$ ($p<.05$), $.10$ ($p<.01$), $.13$ ($p<.001$)- Two Tailed

Inter-factorial correlations indicate that all the factors are highly and significantly correlated with each other and measuring the same construct. The Cronbach's Alpha for factors varying from 0.787 to 0.825, and effect-size for teacher's occupational stress dimensions varies from 0.624 to 0.680 and shows high strength of relationship among items for the respective dimensions. The effect size have been drawn on the line chart and shown as figure 1.

Figure 1 Effect Size

Validity

Content (Face and logical) validity of the scale was verified by number of experts, academicians and professionals. Good correspondence was found to exist between the scale results and the considered judgments of experienced observers.

There are various methods to establish construct validity of the tool. Hence, quite a few of them are having limitations as role of time and existence of subjectivity in experts' ratings. To overcome these limitations, Exploratory Factor analysis with Varimax rotation was used to establish the construct validity of the tool. Data screening was carried out in order to overcome existence of multicollinearity (i.e. items that are highly correlated) and singularity (i.e. items that are perfectly correlated) in the scale.

Table 5

Factorial Structure of Teacher's Self efficacy (TSES)

Factors	Item Numbers	Factor Loadings	Variance	
			PCT of Variance	Cum. Variance
I	Work Characteristics (X1)	.721-.497	22.976	22.976
II	Situational Characteristics (X2)	.715-.449	15.391	38.367
III	Personal Characteristics (X3)	.712-.480	12.179	50.546

Using a more structured method, confirmatory factor analyses presents evidence of the measures' convergent and discriminant validity. Three factors emerged and confirmed in the factor analysis. The percent of variance accounted by factors varies from 12.18 to 22.98%. In summing up all the six factors explained 50.55% of the total variance. The factorial validity of the scale is highly satisfactory.

Conclusion

Reliability, validity and stability data based on 600 school/college teachers showed that Teacher's Occupational Stress scale has quite satisfactory psychometric characteristics. It can be concluded that the Teacher's Occupational Stress scale is highly reliable and valid to measure the Occupational Stress of School/college teachers. The more structured, exploratory factor analysis provided evidence of the construct or factorial validity which was found to be highly satisfactory. Inter-factorial correlations indicate that all the factors are significantly correlated with each other and measuring the same construct which confirms inter-factorial validity of the scale. The effect size shows high strength of relationship among items for the respective sub dimensions of Occupational Stress scale. The results of the present investigation exhibited that the bilingual version of Teacher's Occupational Stress scale can be used for training, assessment, intervention and research purposes.

Implications

In this study we have sought to standardize the Teacher's Occupational Stress scale on the basis of the representative sample. It has been established that psychometric properties (reliability and validity) of the scale are highly satisfying. Accordingly, the first major practical contribution of present research is that it provides sufficient background to measure Teacher's Occupational Stress of the same population. After reviewing a number of research studies it can be opined that three proposed facets are sufficient to explain the Teacher's Occupational Stress. Our study, being of an exploratory and interpreting in nature, raises a number of opportunities for future research. More research will in fact be necessary to refine and further elaborate our novel findings.

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